

Exploring the Dark Energy Phenomenon: The Impact of the Dark Energy Survey

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The Dark Energy Survey (DES) was enabled by the construction of the Dark Energy Camera (DECam), the prime focus instrument on the Víctor M. Blanco 4-meter Telescope at Cerro Tololo Inter-American Observatory (CTIO), a program of NSF's NOIRLab. The scientific motivation for DES — constraining the properties of dark energy by deep images — was developed in the early 2000s and drove the initial concept for the camera. The camera needed to have a wide field of view, which implied large correcting lenses and tight control of aberrations and flexure. This in turn implied the camera would have to be massive

At the same time, in the early 2000s, NOIRLab (then NOAO) was exploring what role the Kitt Peak National Observatory (KPNO) and CTIO 4m telescopes could have in the era of modern 6- to 8-meter telescopes. Using the telescopes to investigate the then newly discovered phenomenon of dark energy was at the top of the list.

Astronomers realized that the older massive steel equatorial mounts of the Mayall 4-meter Telescope at KPNO and the Blanco at CTIO were ideal for mounting heavy instruments at the prime focus — a perfect match of scientific need with practical capabilities. Thus was born the partnership where the construction of DECam was the responsibility of Fermilab, assisted by many DES international institutional partners, while the team at CTIO was responsible for fitting DECam to the Blanco, replacing its entire top end. The data system was also a joint project, involving the National Center for Supercomputing Applications (NCSA) and other DES institutions, as well as NOIRLab.

The agreement among the various agencies was that DES would be granted 30% of the observing time for five years, in return for supporting public access to the instrument during this period, including a data processing pipeline and other tools. At the end of DES observing, DECam was then to

become a facility instrument for CTIO, completing NOIRLab's early vision for a world-class wide-field imager available to the general community.

What Is Dark Energy?

The discovery of the accelerated expansion of the Universe just before the turn of the millennium (see the Perlmutter and the Riess & Schmidt articles in this Science Highlights section) revolutionized our understanding of the cosmos, leading to the reintroduction of the cosmological constant or some other unknown form of energy to justify why the expansion of the Universe is speeding up. This mysterious substance accounts for nearly 70% of the total energy in the present-day Universe, yet we know very little about what it could be or how it behaves. It is most commonly modeled as a property of space itself, rather than a particle or field. Its existence was first proposed to justify the observed accelerated expansion of the Universe discovered from constructing *Hubble* diagrams using Type Ia supernovae.

If the equation of state for dark energy is constant over time with a value of -1 , it would suggest dark energy is simply a cosmological constant Λ , consistent with what Einstein proposed in 1917. However, some cosmologists have suggested that the dark energy equation of state may be

changing with cosmological time, such that dark energy is something other than Λ . This would have significant implications for our understanding of the Universe and its future. To help unravel this cosmic enigma, cosmologists are building and conducting an amazing array of experiments to measure the properties of dark energy, and one of the most powerful to date is the DES.

The Dark Energy Survey

DES is an international collaboration of scientists who are studying dark energy using data taken with the powerful 570-megapixel DECam mounted on the Blanco telescope at CTIO in Chile. DES is capable of capturing images of up to 100,000 galaxies in a single snapshot, allowing cosmologists to study the distribution of galaxies and their properties in unprecedented detail. The primary goal of DES is to measure the equation of state for dark energy, which describes how dark energy changes over time. To achieve this, DES scientists use many different methods to study the Universe and how it changes over time, including the main four methods described below.

One approach is to use Type Ia supernovae (SN) as cosmic distance markers to infer the distances to galaxies. Their brightness tells us their distance, and their spectral properties tell us their recession velocity, which together let us infer the evolution of the Universe's expansion rate to constrain the properties of dark energy.

A second approach is to use Baryon Acoustic Oscillations (BAO), a feature imprinted in the large-scale distribution of galaxies that originated from acoustic waves in the baryons of the early universe. DES measures this feature on the sky from the galaxies, allowing us to probe the expansion rate of the Universe in an independent way.

A third approach is to investigate the abundance of massive galaxy clusters. The tug of war between gravity and dark energy means that the sizes of those galaxy clusters are sensitive to the evolution of dark energy over time. More dark energy means faster expansion, which means fewer massive clusters can form. Thus, the abundance of massive galaxy clusters over time can also expose the properties of dark energy.

A fourth approach is to study the weak gravitational lensing and the clustering of galaxies in the large-scale structure of the Universe. Weak lensing involves measuring the distortion of light from distant galaxies by the gravitational pull of intervening matter, including dark matter. Measured on the scale of modern galaxy surveys, weak lensing provides a direct probe of the structure and history of the low-redshift

This figure shows the weak lensing convergence map in the footprint of the Dark Energy Survey (purple), combined with stars in the Milky Way. This map shows the matter distribution along the line of sight projected in two dimensions. The lighter the color, the more matter is accumulated along the line of sight. *Credit: N. Jeffrey/University College London and the DES Collaboration*

Dark Matter map from DES observations

Universe. Alternatively, one could map the positions of the same galaxies on the sky; tracing the correlations in galaxy density provides an alternative measurement of the large scale matter distribution. The combination of these two effects is typically known as the “3x2pt” probes, since it consists of three two-point measurements.

Although each of the four approaches is powerful in their own right, weak lensing and galaxy clustering are the most sensitive to different cosmological parameters and to different systematic effects than supernovae and BAO. Combining all four observational techniques allows for much more robust measurements of dark energy parameters and helps reduce the impact of systematic uncertainties.

The Impact of the Dark Energy Survey

DES has achieved a significant leap in the quality and quantity of data available to study dark energy. We have already released a catalog of over 800 million objects in the sky, including over half a billion galaxies, and we will soon be releasing data that approximately doubles the number of distant supernovae ever measured. Our preliminary results using half of this data achieve a 10% constraint on w , and our final analysis of our full dataset is currently underway, with results expected in 2024.

The most important aspect of this experiment is that it is the first to use a combined-probes approach. This approach has the potential to reveal new physics and cosmic mysteries that may lead to an even deeper understanding of our Universe, because it is when different measurements of the same thing disagree that new physics can be revealed. In particular, by combining 3x2pt with BAO and supernova (SN) from DES, we found an improvement of about 40% in the constraining power compared to 3x2pt alone, allowing to constrain the dark energy equation of state, at a precision of 10% with half our final data. This is about twice as constraining as the Cosmic Microwave Background alone can do currently, and only a factor of two less constraining than the combined power of most other low-redshift data together. The probes DES is using are entirely independent from previous early-Universe-based studies, yet this result is in agreement with previous measurements, suggesting that the equation of state for dark energy is indeed consistent with a cosmological constant. This result is significant, as it supports the standard cosmological model and our understanding of the Universe’s evolution and future.

In addition to the four dark energy probes described above, DES provides the data to perform a variety of other tests on dark energy and cosmology, as well as studies beyond cosmology. For example, combining gravitational waves and galaxies from DES data allows us to constrain the expansion rate of the Universe. Similar constraints can be achieved using strong gravitational lensed galaxies in DES, followed up by space-based telescopes. DES has also enabled new opportunities to study other astrophysical phenomena besides dark energy. Throughout the years, we have measured how galaxies form and evolve, discovered rare solar system objects including the most distant and massive comet, and even offered insights on what properties dark matter particles could possess.

Another significant and lasting impact of the DES project has been the development of new techniques for cosmological observations and calibration. DES has pioneered new methods for measuring galaxy shapes and photometric redshifts and has developed new algorithms for managing and analyzing large datasets. The primary DES cosmological analyses have also sustained a commitment to developing the first uniformly blinded multi-probe experiment — that is, DES scientists hide the true information about the Universe in their data even from themselves, until they are sure the data are robust. This protects us from confirmation bias in what we learn about the Universe in DES. These advancements have important implications for future cosmological projects and will pave the way for further discoveries.

A final important aspect of DES is its commitment to open data sharing. Nearly all of the DES data is publicly available to anyone who wishes to use it, and cosmologists from around the world have already made use of this data to carry out new studies and make new discoveries. This open approach to data sharing is critical for advancing our understanding of the Universe, as it enables more cosmologists to participate in the scientific process and collaborate on new ideas and discoveries.

As we wrap up the main DES dark energy analyses in the coming years, we look forward to sharing more about what we learn from the Universe, both through fundamental discoveries and via our legacy of technical advances. DES’s legacy will also continue for many years to come, with future surveys and missions building on its findings and methods and pushing the boundaries of our understanding of the Universe even further.